

Qualitative study on integration ... (Adamu, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080476>

Qualitative study on integration of Social-Emotional-Learning to improve learning outcome at Basic level of Education in North-East, Nigeria

Adamu, Omar Babale¹

umarulfaruku@gmail.com

08026267574 (10 fonts)

Mohammed Ali Gajiram²

mohammedaligajiram@gmail.com

08065476355

Adamu Babale³

babaleadamu@yahoo.com

08036525706

Shettima Zainab Bukar⁴

zainabshettimab@gmail.com

08028054732

¹Yobe State University, Nigeria

²Ramat Polytechnics Maiduguri, Nigeria

³Nuhu Sanusi Polytechnic Dutse, Jigawa State, Nigeria

⁴Umar Ibn Ibrahim College of Education, Science & Technology Bama, Borno State

Abstract

This study explores the integration of Social Emotional Learning (SEL) in improving learning outcomes in Northeast Nigeria, a region grappling with conflict and socio-economic challenges. SEL promotes emotional intelligence, resilience, and interpersonal skills, which are critical for academic and life success. It was a descriptive survey research design that adopted a using qualitative approach was adopted for the study. Data were collected using focus group discussion and in-depth interviews conducted with teachers, students, and policymakers in Borno Adamawa and Yobe states, Nigeria alongside a review of SEL program documents implemented in similar contexts. The data collected was analysed using thematic analysis. The study concludes that Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) has the potential to enhance education, improve emotional stability, promote peacebuilding, and reduce conflict in Northeast Nigeria. Equipping students with SEL skills fosters resilience, social interaction, and academic success in conflict-affected areas. For SEL to be effective, it requires cultural adaptation, community involvement in policy formation, and teacher capacity building to ensure widespread adoption and sustainability. Based on the findings the recommends that the Northeast states government should develop policies to integrate Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) into the curriculum, with adaptations for conflict-affected areas; Train and re-train teachers on SEL programs should be prioritised to equip educators with the necessary skills and resources for effective implementation; and foster collaboration between the government, parents, religious leaders, and local communities is essential to address cultural concerns, ensure acceptance, and promote the sustainability of SEL initiatives.

Keyword: Socio-Emotional Learning, Positive Social Relationship, Academic Outcomes, Emotional Well-being.

Introduction

The Northeast region of Nigeria has been significantly affected by prolonged insurgency, displacement, and socio-economic challenges, resulting in widespread disruptions to education. Many schools have been destroyed, access to quality education is limited, and students face high levels of trauma and psychosocial stress. These challenges have led to poor academic performance, low school attendance, and a lack of social and emotional skills among students. Social Emotional Learning (SEL) offers a framework to address these issues by fostering emotional regulation, empathy, and interpersonal skills (Durlak et al., 2011). In conflict-affected settings like Northeast Nigeria, SEL programs have been shown to promote resilience

Qualitative study on integration ... (Adamu, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080476>

and psychosocial well-being among children (World Bank, 2021). By addressing the emotional scars of conflict, SEL can create a conducive learning and personal growth environment. This study explores how SEL can enhance educational outcomes in Northeast Nigeria, focusing on its application in conflict-affected settings. It highlights the importance of integrating SEL into the education system to build resilience, improve academic performance, and positive social relationships and promote long-term socio-emotional well-being. The integration of SEL in the Nigerian educational frameworks remains limited because only little of stakeholders know its effectiveness in the conflict-ridden context. This study tends to address the gap by exploring how SEL can be integrated into the national curriculum and improve educational outcomes and the socio-economic and well-being of students in Northeast, Nigeria. More so, to identify problems of SEL implementation and profound solutions in the region, providing evidence-based recommendations for policymakers, educators and stakeholders.

The following research questions guide the study.

- i. What are the academic benefits of implementing SEL activities for students at the basic school level of education in Northeast, Nigeria?
- ii. How do the SEL activities influence the emotional well-being and social skills of students in conflict-affected communities?
- iii. What are the roles of teachers, parents and education policymakers in the integration of SEL into the in North-East, Nigeria Basic education system?
- iv. How can the SEL program in Basic education be adapted to align with the socio-cultural, and economic realities of Northeast Nigeria?
- v. What are the challenges and possible solutions of SEL implementation at Basic school level of education in the Northeast Nigeria education system?

A descriptive research design adopting a qualitative approach aims to systematically describe the situation of students in Northeast Nigeria and the impact of SEL programs in educational settings of the region. Data were collected using focus group discussion and in-depth interviews conducted with teachers, students, and policymakers in Borno Adamawa and Yobe states, Nigeria alongside a review of SEL program documents implemented in similar contexts. The data collected was analysed using thematic analysis.

Social Emotional Learning (SEL)

Durlak et al. (2011) defined SEL as the process through which individuals acquire and effectively apply the knowledge, attitudes, and skills necessary to understand and manage emotions, set and achieve positive goals, feel and show empathy for others, establish and maintain positive relationships, and make responsible decisions. SEL is defined as the process of developing self-awareness, self-control, and interpersonal skills that are vital for school, work, and life success. Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL, 2022). Taylor et al. (2017) SEL involves structured educational programs that focus on developing emotional intelligence and interpersonal skills to enhance students' ability to succeed academically and socially.

Importance of Social Emotional Learning (SEL) at Basic education level

Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) has demonstrated significant positive impacts in Northeast Nigeria, a region affected by conflict and displacement. Studies indicate that SEL programs help children and adolescents develop emotional regulation skills, and enhance academic outcomes, enabling them to manage stress, anxiety, and trauma more effectively.

The Role of SEL in Enhancing Academic Outcomes at Basic education level

SEL helps students in Northeast Nigeria improve their focus, persistence, and classroom engagement, resulting in better academic performance. Research has shown that SEL improves students' academic outcomes by fostering self-regulation and motivation, which are critical for learning, especially in conflict-affected settings (Durlak et al., 2011). Studies have consistently shown that SEL improves academic outcomes, reduces behavioural problems, and enhances emotional well-being (Taylor et al., 2017). For conflict-affected regions, SEL provides a critical tool for helping students cope with trauma and rebuild their lives. The implementation of SEL in Northeast Nigeria has shown that emotional and social skills are foundational to academic success. Students participating in SEL programs exhibit better classroom behaviour, increased motivation, and enhanced concentration, leading to improved academic performance (Hassan, R., Olaniyi, A., & Yusuf, K., 2021). Teachers have reported that SEL practices, such as mindfulness exercises and collaborative learning, create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment, even in resource-constrained settings.

Qualitative study on integration ... (Adamu, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080476>

The Role of SEL in Enhanced Emotional and Social Competence in Basic Education

In conflict-affected areas, children often experience trauma that impacts their ability to learn and interact socially. SEL programs provide tools to address these issues by helping students develop emotional regulation and resilience. Studies conducted in post-conflict regions such as South Sudan and Syria found that SEL improved students' emotional well-being, reduced aggressive behaviours, and fostered better peer relationships (World Bank, 2021). Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) has demonstrated significant positive impacts in Northeast Nigeria, a region affected by conflict and displacement. Studies indicate that SEL programs help children and adolescents develop emotional regulation skills, enabling them to manage stress, anxiety, and trauma more effectively. For instance, interventions implemented in internally displaced persons (IDP) camps showed marked improvements in participants' ability to identify and manage emotions, which contributed to better mental health outcomes (Obiakor et al., 2020). SEL addresses the emotional needs of children by providing a safe environment for expressing feelings and managing stress. This is critical in Northeast Nigeria, where children face multiple stressors such as displacement, poverty, and insecurity (UNICEF, 2022). Social Emotional Learning (SEL) equips individuals with essential competencies such as self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making (CASEL, 2022). These competencies are not only foundational for academic success but also for overall well-being. Studies have shown that SEL helps mitigate behavioural issues, enhances emotional resilience, and reduces symptoms of anxiety and depression (Taylor et al., 2017).

The Role of SEL in Promoting Peacebuilding and Reducing Community Conflict in Basic education

SEL plays a critical role in peacebuilding efforts in Northeast Nigeria. By addressing the root causes of aggression and promoting empathy, SEL initiatives help reduce tensions between conflicting groups. Programs like the “Education in Emergencies” framework have incorporated SEL to teach nonviolent communication and collaborative problem-solving, fostering mutual understanding among youth from diverse backgrounds (UNICEF, 2021). Furthermore, SEL contributes to reintegration efforts for former child soldiers and other marginalized groups. Skills in emotional regulation and interpersonal interaction are crucial for their rehabilitation and acceptance back into society (Benson et al., 2020). These initiatives also empower young people to become agents of peace within their communities, thereby reducing cycles of violence and fostering long-term stability. By teaching empathy, conflict resolution, and interpersonal skills, SEL fosters positive peer relationships and reduces bullying and aggression. These skills are important in fostering social cohesion in a region marked by ethnic and religious tensions (Ajayi et al., 2020). Adaptability of SEL to align with the sociocultural and economic realities of Northeast. The SEL program can be adapted to align with the socio-cultural, and economic realities of Northeast Nigeria.

Cultural Relevance and Sensitivity in Basic education

The integration of local values and norms into SEL programs is crucial for their acceptance and effectiveness. As noted by Elias et al. (1997), culturally relevant SEL programs foster greater engagement among students and communities. For instance, incorporating community-centric practices such as communal harmony and respect for elders into SEL frameworks ensures alignment with local traditions. Furthermore, engaging religious and community leaders to advocate for SEL programs enhances credibility and local ownership, which is critical in culturally conservative regions like Northeast Nigeria.

Trauma-Informed Practices in Basic education

Children in conflict-affected regions often face significant psychological distress. Taylor et al. (2017) highlight that trauma-informed SEL approaches, such as emotional regulation and mindfulness, can help children process traumatic experiences and rebuild resilience. The findings reinforce the need for SEL programs in Northeast Nigeria to include components that address trauma and provide psychosocial support, which is particularly relevant given the region's ongoing insecurity and displacement issues.

Community Involvement in Basic education

The study also underscores the importance of involving parents and local communities in the design and implementation of SEL programs. According to Adamu (2019), community participation enhances the sustainability and effectiveness of educational interventions by fostering a sense of collective responsibility. Engaging parents through workshops and mobilizing community resources ensures that SEL initiatives are both cost-effective and widely supported.

Qualitative study on integration ... (Adamu, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080476>

Economic Feasibility in Basic education

Given the economic constraints in Northeast Nigeria, SEL programs must be designed to be low-cost and resource efficiency. Durlak et al. (2011) argues that SEL programs that leverage existing resources and train local facilitators are more sustainable in low-income settings. The findings advocate for the use of locally available materials and volunteer training to minimize costs while maximizing impact.

Flexibility in Delivery in Basic education

Embedding SEL into existing school curricula and informal education settings is essential for reaching displaced and underserved populations. Zins et al. (2004) emphasize that integrating SEL into core subjects like religious studies or civic education reduces the burden on teachers while ensuring that all students benefit from these programs. In Northeast Nigeria, this approach can be particularly beneficial for students in IDP camps or informal learning centres.

Monitoring and Evaluation in Basic education

Finally, the study highlights the importance of monitoring and evaluating SEL programs to ensure their relevance and effectiveness. Collecting community feedback and assessing outcomes such as improved student behaviour and attendance are critical steps in refining and sustaining these programs (UNICEF, 2022).

Discussion of Findings

Improved Academic Outcomes through SEL in Basic education

The findings revealed that students who participated in SEL programs demonstrated better academic outcomes, particularly in literacy and numeracy. Teachers reported that SEL-equipped students showed increased focus, perseverance, and tolerance, leading to better academic performance. These outcomes align with Durlak et al. (2011), who found that SEL interventions improve academic performance. The study corroborates Ajayi et al.'s (2020) findings in Nigerian IDP camps, where SEL improved student engagement and learning outcomes, even in challenging environments.

Enhanced Emotional and Social Competence in Basic education

Findings show that both parents and teachers testified that students attending schools with Socio-Emotional Learning programs have acquired emotional and social skills. Students have been more confident and assertive in the expression of their emotions and exhibit good social behaviours, resolving peer conflicts and building positive relationships. Teachers also noted there is a decline in classroom aggression and bullying fostering a better collaborative learning environment. These findings align with the findings of the World Bank (2021) which demonstrated that Social Emotional Learning in conflict-affected communities like South Sudan reduced aggressive behaviour and improved peer relationships. These findings are consistent with the World Bank (2021) study, which demonstrated that SEL in conflict-affected regions such as South Sudan reduced aggressive behaviours and improved peer relationships. Furthermore, Taylor et al. (2017) highlighted that Social Emotional Learning enhances long-term emotional stability, which improves classroom dynamics. The results emphasise that SEL programs address emotional and social deficits in conflict-affected children, promoting interpersonal skills critical for personal growth and community rebuilding.

Promoting Peacebuilding and Reducing Community Conflict in Basic education.

Teachers and parents highlighted how SEL can address the root causes of aggression by teaching children nonviolent communication and collaborative problem-solving skills. This view is consistent with the “Education in Emergencies” framework, which incorporates SEL to promote mutual understanding among diverse groups (UNICEF, 2021). The alignment of these perspectives underscores the critical role SEL plays in reducing tensions and building peaceful communities. The findings also support the notion that SEL is vital for the reintegration of former child soldiers and marginalized youth. Parents and teachers noted the importance of emotional regulation and interpersonal skills in helping these groups reintegrate into society. This is echoed by Benson et al. (2020), who emphasize the transformative role of SEL in rehabilitation and acceptance, empowering young people to act as agents of peace. Both parents and teachers agree that teaching empathy, conflict resolution,

Qualitative study on integration ... (Adamu, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080476>

and interpersonal skills fosters positive relationships among students and reduces bullying and aggression. This aligns with Ajayi et al. (2020), who highlighted the significance of SEL in promoting social cohesion in regions characterized by ethnic and religious tensions. These skills are critical for building harmonious interactions and addressing the challenges of diversity in the region. The shared perspectives of parents and teachers in Northeast Nigeria reinforce the importance of integrating SEL into educational programs to address not only academic challenges but also social and emotional issues. By fostering peacebuilding, promoting social cohesion, and supporting marginalized groups, SEL contributes to long-term stability and community resilience in the region (Adamu, 2019).

Roles of Teachers, Parents, and Policymakers in the Integration of SEL

The roles of teachers in implementing SEL in Basic education

The teachers and parents considered teachers as the primary implementors of SEL, creating a conducive and supportive classroom where students can develop social and emotional competencies. The teachers play a vital role in modelling SEL skills such as respect, tolerance, remembering, focusing, empathy, communication and conflict-solving for the students. “Teachers can observe students' emotional and social needs, providing targeted support to those struggling with trauma or behavioural challenges”. “Through strategies like mindfulness exercises, peer group activities, and positive reinforcement, teachers can help students manage stress and build resilience. Teachers collaborate with parents to ensure consistency between school and home environment in fostering SEL.

The roles of parents in implementing SEL in Basic education

The study asserted that parents provide a supportive home environment where parents reinforce SEL principles by encouraging emotional expression, empathy, logical thinking, and rational decision-making in their children. “We work closely with teachers to understand SEL goals and provide feedback about our children's attitudes and behaviours at home.” Parent. “The parent advocate for the inclusion of SEL into the school’s curriculum and voicing the importance of SEL and education to community leaders, policymakers and political class.” Teachers.

The roles of policymakers in implementing SEL Basic education

The findings of the study show that policymakers provide funding for SEL programs teacher training, SEL curriculum development and other materials necessary for effective SEL implementations. They set clear guidance for integrating SEL into schools with flexibility for culturally and religiously sensitive and regional adaptations. “Policymakers incorporate SEL programs into regional and national educational policies, ensuring it becomes a standardized part of the curriculum and creating safe and stable learning environment” Parent Adamawa. “Government are responsible for setting a framework to assess the relevance, coherence, efficiency and effectiveness of the SEL program by continuous data collection and analysis on the children academic performance, attendance, emotional well-being and social behaviours to inform decision-making.” Borno Teacher.

Adaptability of SEL to align with the sociocultural and economic realities of Northeast

The findings of the study revealed that the perspectives of teachers and students in Northeast Nigeria aligned with existing literature on the adaptability of SEL with norms, values and beliefs of the people of the area to achieve its objective of improving educational outcomes. Teachers and parents recognize the need for culturally appropriate SEL programs to address the socio-economic and trauma-related challenges faced by students. This aligns with the findings of Elias et al. (1997), who emphasized the importance of tailoring SEL programs to local values and norms for greater acceptance and impact. Additionally, this study revealed that teachers' and parents' participation in the implementation of SEL mirrors Adamu's (2019) that community participation enhances school enrolment, attendance, and retention. Similarly, the recognition of trauma-informed practices for rebuilding resilience in children of Northeast Nigeria echoes the findings of Taylor et al. (2017), highlighting the necessity of equipping schools with programs to support students' emotional well-being in conflict-affected areas. These aligned views underscore the importance of designing SEL programs that reflect local realities, involve key stakeholders, and address both academic and psychosocial needs, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes.

Qualitative study on integration ... (Adamu, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080476>

Challenges in SEL Implementation in Basic education

Although most respondents viewed SEL is playing a vital role in managing children's socio-emotional behaviour the study revealed there are significant challenges in implementing SEL in Northeast Nigeria, as outlined by teachers and parents as follows:

- i. Inadequate Socio-Emotional Learning Teachers: There is a limited number of teachers undergone SEL training, and most of the teachers lack the skills to handle SEL lessons in their respective classrooms.
- ii. Teachers and parents felt that most of the available SEL materials were borrowed from the white men's land concepts, around respect, emotional expression and conflict resolution needed to be adapted into the local northeast context which is aligned with the norms and values of people of the Northeast. This finding resonates with Ajayi et al.'s (2020) recommendation that the SEL program must be culturally sensitive to ensure acceptance and effectiveness.
- iii. Limited SEL Resources: The findings of this study revealed that most of the in Northeast Nigeria have limited or no basic SEL resources to implement SEL programs in their schools' systemic challenges in conflict-affected areas as also highlighted by UNICEF (2022) and call for targeted investment in education in such regions.
- iv. The study identified a gap in teacher training and policy support for SEL implementation. While the benefits of SEL were evident, its integration into the curriculum remains limited.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the SEL program has the transformative potential of enhancing educational outcomes, improving emotional stability, promoting peacebuilding and reducing community conflict in Northeast Nigeria. Equipping students with essential skills can address the unique challenges of conflict-affected areas, fostering resilience, positive social interaction and academic success. Having culturally adapted SEL programs, involving the local community in the formation of SEL policy formation and implementation, and teachers' capacity building to ensure widespread adoption of SEL programs are the preconditions of SEL achieving its purpose.

Recommendations

Despite these challenges, the findings underscore the potential of SEL to transform education in Northeast Nigeria. Key recommendations include:

1. The Northeast state government should provide policies for the integration of SEL into the state curriculum and implementation in classrooms with specific adaptations for conflict-affected areas.
2. The Northeast state government should train and re-train large-scale teachers on programs focused on SEL and should be prioritized to equip educators with the necessary skills and resources required for the implementation of the SEL programs.
3. Collaboratively involvement and participation of state governments parents, religious leaders, and local communities in SEL initiatives can address cultural concerns and ensure buy-in and sustainability.
4. This suggests that the inclusion of SEL in schools across Northeast Nigeria could address significant educational disparities caused by prolonged conflict, providing students with the skills needed to overcome academic and personal challenges.

References

- Adamu, O., B. (2019). Role of community in primary school administration in Jigawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Development, 45*(3), 123–135.
- Ajayi, K., Adeniran, A., & Adeola, G. (2020). The role of social-emotional learning in conflict-affected areas: Insights from Nigerian IDP camps. *Journal of Educational Development, 45*(3), 123–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jed.2020.04.015>
- Benson, P. L., Scales, P. C., Hamilton, S. F., & Sesma, A. (2020). Positive youth development: Theory, research, and applications. In *Handbook of youth and young adulthood* (3rd ed., pp. 118–137).
- Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL). (2020). *What is SEL?* Retrieved from <https://casel.org/what-is-sel/>
- Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child Development, 82*(1), 405–432. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01564.x>

Qualitative study on integration ... (Adamu, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080476>

- Elias, M. J., Zins, J. E., Weissberg, R. P., Frey, K. S., Greenberg, M. T., Haynes, N. M., Kessler, R., Schwab-Stone, M. E., & Shriver, T. P. (1997). *Promoting social and emotional learning: Guidelines for educators*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Hassan, R., Olaniyi, A., & Yusuf, K. (2021). The role of social and emotional learning in reducing community conflict in Northeast Nigeria. *Journal of Peace Education*, 18(2), 159–175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17400201.2021.1874989>
- Jones, S. M., Bailey, R., & Jacob, R. (2019). Social-emotional learning: A new synthesis. *The Future of Children*, 27(1), 13–32. <https://doi.org/10.1353/foc.2019.0001>
- Mercy Corps. (2019). *Building bridges: The impact of SEL in fragile and conflict-affected regions*. Retrieved from <https://www.mercycorps.org>
- Olatunde, A. M., Adamu, Y., & Ibrahim, K. (2022). Building resilience through SEL in displaced populations: Evidence from Northeast Nigeria.
- Osofsky, J. D. (1999). The impact of violence on children. *The Future of Children*, 9(3), 33–49. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1602780>
- Osher, D., Cantor, P., Berg, J., Steyer, L., & Rose, T. (2016). Drivers of human development: How relationships and context shape learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 21(1), 1–31.
- Taylor, R. D., Oberle, E., Durlak, J. A., & Weissberg, R. P. (2017). Promoting positive youth development through school-based social and emotional learning interventions: A meta-analysis of follow-up effects. *Child Development*, 88(4), 1156–1171. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12864>
- UNICEF. (2022). *Education under attack: Challenges for children in Northeast Nigeria*. Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org>
- UNICEF. (2021). *Education in emergencies: Learning for peace in Nigeria*. UNICEF Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria>
- World Bank. (2021). *Education and resilience: Lessons from conflict-affected countries*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org>
- World Bank. (2018). *The promise of education for conflict-affected youth: Social and emotional learning in Nigeria*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org>
- World Bank. (2016). *Education crisis in Northeast Nigeria: Background report*. World Bank.
- Zins, J. E., Weissberg, R. P., Wang, M. C., & Walberg, H. J. (2004). *Building academic success on social and emotional learning: What does the research say?* Teachers College Press